

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ORGANICALLY MODIFIED LAYERED ZINC PHENYLPHOSPHONATE/POLY(1,4-BUTYLENE CARBONATE-CO-TEREPHTHALATE)S NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the biocompatible organic dodecylamine and octadecylamine were selected to modify layered zinc phenylphosphonates (PPZns) (designated as C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn). C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn were added into the Poly(butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT) polymer matrix as nucleating agents. The fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra of C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn contain additional absorption peaks at 3300 cm⁻¹ and 1370-1000 cm⁻¹, which are attributed to dodecylamine and octadecylamine in corporation into PPZn. The results of wide angle x-ray diffraction (WAXD) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) demonstrate that PPZn layers were intercalated by PBCT polymer chains. The crystallization properties of nanocomposites were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Experimental results of non-isothermal and isothermal melt crystallization kinetics showed that PPZn had a significant impact on crystallization behavior of PBCT. With the presence of organic modified-PPZn, the T_c of PBCT increase significantly. Upon the addition of 5% C₁₂-PPZn, the crystallization half-times at 125 °C of the PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn composite decrease from 7.68 min of pure PBCT to 2.09 min of 5 wt% nanocomposite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Combining low density, high specific strength, good corrosion resistance and low cost, plastics are the workhorse material of the modern economy. However, they cause serious environmental pollution problems. Biodegradable aliphatic polyesters (APCs) have aroused great concern as compostable alternatives for persistent petroleum-based polymers. APCs are noticeable for their unique properties, including superior biodegradability, no-toxicity and biocompatibility[1-3]. Poly(butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT), a new APC made from dimethyl carbonate (DMC), dimethyl terephthalate (DMT) and 1,4-butylene (BD), can be potentially applied in the biomedical field. Attractively, the prepared PBCTs with 40–50 mol% terephthalate units showed excellent thermal properties comparable to the compostable aliphatic polyesters currently available on the market [4, 5]. The use of nano-reinforcements into the polymers has exhibited considerable promise for designing green polymeric materials with desired properties. Depending on the processing conditions and the matrix/nano-reinforcements affinity, different nanocomposites structures can be obtained when a layered clay is associated with a polymer[6, 7]. Phenylphosphonate (PPZn), also known as inorganic layered material and a new kind of benign filler, has attracted much attention due to accelerate the crystallization of various biodegradable polymers[8-11]. In the previous study, Chen, et al. has used two long-chain alkylamines, dodecylamine and octadecylamine to intercalate into the interlayer spacing of PPZn[12]. The modified PPZn was then successfully mixed with PBSA to fabricate the PBSA/organically-modified PPZn nanocomposites through the melt-mixing technique. In this work, the organically modified PPZn (C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn) were used as nucleating agents (NAs) to incorporate into the PBCT and to investigate their effect on the crystallization behavior of PBCT.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Dimethyl carbonate (DMC), dimethyl terephthalate (DMT), 1,4-butylene (BD), Zinc nitrate hexahydrate, dodecylamine and octadecylamine were purchased from Alfa Aesar. NaOH was purchased from Honeywell Fluka. Phenylphosphonic acid was purchased from Acros Organics. All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

2.2 Synthesis of PBCT

Biodegradable poly(butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) were prepared by a two-step melt polycondensation method, transesterification, and polycondensation as described by Lee, et al[5]. DMC, DMT, BD and the catalyst NaOH were added to a four-necked round-bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, nitrogen inlet, reflux condenser and thermometer. Then the mixture was heated to 120°C for 1 h under a nitrogen atmosphere and stirring. The temperature was then gradually increased to 190°C and maintained for 1 h to ensure unreacted DMC and methanol formed as transesterification byproducts removed completely. The temperature of the distillation head was kept between 60 and 66°C to prevent too much volatilization of DMC. In the second step of polycondensation, a high vacuum was applied slowly to avoid excessive foaming and to minimize oligomer sublimation. The temperature was then increased to 210 °C slowly and the polycondensation reaction was carried out for 6 h.

2.3 Synthesis of organically modified-PPZn

The phenylphosphonic acid zinc salt was prepared according to the previous reported paper[13]. Typically, 1 g of phenylphosphonic acid was dissolved in 40 mL of water. One equivalent of ZnCl₂ dissolved in 20 mL of water was added to the stirred phenylphosphonic acid solution, followed by the addition of sufficient 0.1 mol/L aqueous NaOH to reach pH 5-6, and then stirred in water at 60 °C for 3 days to improve the crystallinity. The sample prepared in this way was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and dried at 150 °C under vacuum for 12 h. The C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZns were prepared by a similar approach reported previously[12]. At first, the amine were dissolve in alcohol. The amine intercalates were prepared by contacting solid, dehydrated PPZn with liquid amines at room temperature for about 3 days. The sample prepared in this way was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and dried at 80 °C under vacuum for 1 h.

2.4 Preparation of PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites

The 1, 3 and 5 wt% PBCT/modified-PPZn composites were prepared by solvent intercalation method. PBCT and modified-PPZn were add into chloroform separately and stirred for 3 hour, then mixed together and stirred for 3 day. All samples were evaporated at room temperature to form a film, and dried under vacuum for 12 h.

2.5 Characterization

Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) measurements was carried out using an X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D8) equipped with a Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation source. The diffraction patterns were recorded at a scanning rate of 1°/min in the range of $2\theta = 2^\circ - 30^\circ$.

Thermal behavior of neat PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn composites was investigated using a Pyris Diamond differential scanning calorimetry instrument (Perkin-Elmer Inc.). The temperature and heat flow were calibrated using an indium standard under nitrogen purging. The samples (5 mg) were heated to 180 °C and held at 180 °C for 3 min to eliminate the thermal and stress histories. Then the samples were cooled to -50 °C at 10 °C·min⁻¹ for the non-isothermal crystallization or quickly cooled to the preset temperature for the isothermal crystallization.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra of all samples were collected on a Perkin-Elmer Paragon 500 FT-IR spectrometer in the wavenumber range between 400 - 4000 cm⁻¹.

TEM micrographs of all samples were operated by a JEOL JEM-2010 operated at an accelerating

voltage of 120 kV. The ultrathin sections were prepared using a Reichert Ultracut ultramicrotome equipped with a diamond knife.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Intercalation into layered zinc phenylphosphonate

Figure 1 shows the FT-IR spectra of C₁₂-PPZn, C₁₈-PPZn, PPZn and organic modifier. The water coordinated to Zn exhibits two O-H stretching bands at 3469 and 3430 cm⁻¹ and a deformation band at 1646 cm⁻¹. For the C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn, the water stretching bands are replaced by three sharper bands at 3300 - 3400 cm⁻¹ representing the NH stretching motion and one absorption peak at 1650 - 1660 cm⁻¹ is due to the NH₂ bending vibration. The peaks located at 1000 - 1370 cm⁻¹ are due to the symmetric deformation of NH₂ and the peaks at 950-650 cm⁻¹ are corresponding to the rocking vibration absorption peak of NH₂[14]. These spectra also contain a weak broad band at 3500 cm⁻¹ due to surface moisture. Free primary amines usually have two sharp bands near 3400 and 3300 cm⁻¹. The shift of the N-H stretching bands toward lower frequency and the presence of one additional stretching band strongly suggest that the amine is coordinated to the metal[15]. The three medium bands in the range 750-650 cm⁻¹ are due to out-of-plane of the benzene ring. These results suggest that dodecylamine and octadecylamine were successfully enter PPZn galleries.

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of (a) PPZn, C₁₂-PPZn and dodecylamine (b) PPZn, C₁₈-PPZn and octadecylamine.

Figure 2 are shown the WAXD patterns of PPZn, C₁₂-PPZn, C₁₈-PPZn, PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites. Three sharp diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 6.06^\circ$, 12.22° and 18.4° are observed, which are corresponding to (010), (020) and (030) planes of PPZn, respectively. It can be observed the diffraction peak of the C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn shifted to the lower angle. According to Bragg's law, the interlayer d spacing of PPZn was increased from 14.6 Å for PPZn to 24.2 Å and 30.0 Å for C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn, respectively. This result indicates that the molecular chains of dodecylamine and octadecylamine were intercalated into PPZn galleries. As shown in this figure, the diffraction peak of C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn were clearly observed for all composite samples. This implies that PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites were not exfoliated by PBCT chains. The diffraction peaks of PBCT at $2\theta = 16.1^\circ$, 17.3° , 20.5° , 23.2° , and 25.1° are corresponding to (0-11), (010), (-111), (100) and (1-11) of the planes of PBCT. It indicated the crystal structure of PBCT is identical to that of PBT[4]. The incorporation of C₁₂-PPZn or C₁₈-PPZn into PBCT did not change the crystalline structure of the nanocomposites. The results of WAXD demonstrate that PPZn layers were intercalated by PBCT polymer chains.

Figure 3. WAXD patterns for (a) PPZn, C₁₂-PPZn, PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and (b) PPZn, C₁₈-PPZn, PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites.

In order to further investigate the dispersion of modified-PPZn in PBCT matrix, the microscopic morphology of nanocomposites was observed by TEM analysis. Figure 4 shows TEM images of PBCT containing 5wt% of C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn, respectively. As shown in Figure 5, the micrographs show that both of 5wt% PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and 5wt% PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites belong to intercalated and agglomerated structures. Based on the analysis results of WAXD and TEM, PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites were identified as the partially intercalated structure. Scheme 1. shows the possible intercalation process of the nanocomposites.

Figure 4. TEM micrographs for (a) 5wt% PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and (b) 5wt% PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites.

Scheme 2. Schematic diagram of adding octadecylamine intercalated PPZn to a PBCT matrix to form nanocomposites.

3.3 Non-isothermal crystallization

The effects of modified-PPZn on the non-isothermal melt-crystallization of PBCT were investigated by DSC. Figure 5 shows the cooling curves of the neat PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites. It is clear that the presence of PPZn leads to a significant increase in the crystallization temperature of PPZn at the cooling rate of 10 °C/min. It suggests that upon a foreign heterogeneous nucleating agent, the PBCT can crystallize at a lower supercooling compared to the neat one. Generally, the crystals formed at higher T_c have larger lamellar thickness.

Figure 5. DSC curves of non-isothermal melt crystallization and for PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites. The cooling rate is 10 °C/min.

3.4 Isothermal crystallization

The isothermal crystallization for the PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites were analyzed using the well-known Avrami equation, and its linear form can be expressed in Eq. (1). [16]

$$\log[-\ln(1 - X_t)] = \log k + n \log t \quad (1)$$

where t is the crystallization time (min). X_t is the relative crystallinity at t , which can be calculated from the integrated area of the DSC curve from 0 to t divided by the integrated area of the whole heat flow curve, as expressed in the following Eq. (2).

$$X_t = \frac{\int_0^t \left(\frac{dH}{dt} \right) dt}{\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{dH}{dt} \right) dt} \quad (2)$$

where n is the Avrami exponent depending on the nature of nucleation and growth geometry of the crystals and k is the overall rate constant related to both nucleation and growth contributions. The Avrami parameters n and k can be obtained from the slopes and intercepts, respectively, of plots of $\log[-\ln(1-X_t)]$ against $\log t$. [11]

The plots of the relative crystallinity (X_t) as a function of the crystallization time (t) for the neat PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites are shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that PBCT took much less time to reach the 100% relative crystallinity after the addition of C_{12} -PPZn and C_{18} -PPZn.

Figure 7 shows that all the samples appear to fit very well with Avrami equation. The Avrami parameters ($t_{1/2}$, n and k) were obtained and are summarized in Table 1. $t_{1/2}$ can be defined as the time when it reaches 50% of the relative crystallinity. Upon incorporation of PPZn, $t_{1/2}$ of PBCT decreased greatly and the crystallization rate increased significantly for a given T_c . At $T_c = 125$ °C, the crystallization of the PBCT took at least 7.68 minutes to complete the crystallization process. It is worth noting that incorporation of the C_{12} -PPZn and C_{18} -PPZn could greatly shorten crystallization time to 2.09 and 2.93 minutes. Figure 8 show the dependency of T_c and $t_{1/2}$. Clearly, the crystallization rate decreases with increasing T_c at the studied temperature range for all the samples. Additionally, PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn composites performed higher crystallization rate than PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn.

Figure 6. The relative crystallinity (X_t) as a function of the crystallization time (t) for PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites melt-crystallized. (a) pure PBCT, (b) 1wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (c) 3wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (d) 5wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (e) 1wt% C_{18} -PPZn, (f) 3wt% C_{12} -PPZn (g) 5wt% C_{12} -PPZn.

Figure 7. The representative Avrami plots of PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites at different T_c for (a) pure PBCT, (b) 1wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (c) 3wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (d) 5wt% C_{12} -PPZn, (e) 1wt% C_{18} -PPZn, (f) 3wt% C_{12} -PPZn (g) 5wt% C_{12} -PPZn.

Sample	non-isothermal		isothermal										
	T_c (°C)	n	$T_c=116$ °C		$T_c=119$ °C		$T_c=122$ °C		$T_c=125$ °C				
			k (min ⁻ⁿ)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
PBCT	98.4	1.91	6.71×10^{-2}	3.40	1.81	4.57×10^{-2}	4.48	1.79	2.94×10^{-2}	5.85	1.75	1.96×10^{-2}	7.68
1wt% PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn	103.2	1.90	2.41×10^{-1}	1.74	1.86	1.57×10^{-1}	2.23	1.77	1.07×10^{-1}	2.86	1.73	7.50×10^{-2}	3.61
3wt% PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn	103.4	1.76	4.38×10^{-1}	1.30	1.70	3.06×10^{-1}	1.62	1.62	2.08×10^{-1}	2.10	1.60	1.36×10^{-1}	2.76
5wt% PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn	105.4	1.74	1.02×10^0	0.80	1.61	6.22×10^{-1}	1.07	1.55	3.72×10^{-1}	1.49	1.55	2.21×10^{-1}	2.09
1wt% PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn	100.4	1.83	2.66×10^{-1}	1.69	1.91	1.30×10^{-1}	2.40	1.90	5.58×10^{-2}	3.77	1.88	3.33×10^{-2}	5.02
3wt% PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn	106.4	1.94	9.13×10^{-1}	0.87	1.84	3.89×10^{-1}	1.37	1.82	1.53×10^{-1}	2.29	1.70	8.60×10^{-2}	3.41
5wt% PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn	108.2	1.93	1.79×10^0	0.61	1.98	6.56×10^{-1}	1.03	1.87	2.28×10^{-1}	1.81	1.94	8.60×10^{-2}	2.93

Table 1. T_c of PBCT in the non-isothermal crystallization, and kinetic parameters of PBCT in the isothermal crystallization (116, 119, 122 and 125 °C) for the PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites.

Figure 8. Dependence of the crystallization half time on T_c for the (a) PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn and (b) PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn nanocomposites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

PBCT/ C_{12} -PPZn and PBCT/ C_{18} -PPZn nanocomposites were identified as the partially intercalated structure. Crystallization kinetics data in the isothermal crystallization process suggest that the crystallization time decreased significantly and crystallization rate increased greatly. The DSC results

showed that C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn were efficient nucleation agents for PBCT and it could increase crystallization temperature obviously at a high cooling rate. It is worth that PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn composites performed higher crystallization rate than PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn. The crystallization performance of PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn sample with the content of C₁₂-PPZn at 5 phr was the best.

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